

THE NEED FOR DEVELOPMENT OF PASTURES ON THE SOUTHERN ISLANDS

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Introduction

Relevance of the theme. One of the most serious threats in the South Aral Sea region in recent years, following the depletion of water resources and global climate change, is the irrational use of these pasture lands. According to the data obtained, pastures occupy 25% of the land area of the globe, providing a green landscape on the surface, an invaluable fodder base for livestock, a microclimate for living organisms. Pastures account for 18.2% (678.5 million ha) of the world's grassland and meadow area in Asia, 18% (84.0 million ha) of the region's total area in Europe, and in the arid regions of Africa (total area of this continent). 66%. Therefore, the prevention of degradation processes in pasture lands, the restoration of pasture productivity, the introduction of new promising high-yielding plant species and increase the efficiency of their use are important in science and science.

Aims and objectives of the research: The objectives of the study are to increase the area and productivity of cultivated pastures and to enrich it with water-resistant crops;

- Determining the productivity of pastures in Karakalpakstan, including cultural pastures;

- Determining the location of existing cultural pastures in the Republic of Karakalpakstan by districts;

- Taking into account the water shortage in the country, the introduction of water-resistant and high-yielding crops in cultural pastures.

The content and solution of the problem. At present, there are 21.1 million hectares of pastures (46.5%) in the Republic of Uzbekistan. scarcity, pollution and degradation of lands, a sharp decline in plant species, climate change require more targeted and efficient use of land resources. For the development of animal husbandry in the country, our government should pay special

attention to pastures and take a number of measures to effectively use existing pastures, increase the area of cultural pastures.

Discussion. In the Republic of Karakalpakstan, located on the shores of the Aral Sea, scientific approaches to global climate change, water scarcity, and increasing salinization of pastures have led to declining pastures and declining productivity. To maintain the stability of the Aral Sea, scientists have re-watered the sea to preserve active life and biodiversity along the Amudarya. Given the shortage of water, it is necessary to sharply reduce the area of aquatic crops. Instead, there are various conclusions among scientists on the cultivation of drought-tolerant and fertile crops, the use of hydrogels, the development of natural and cultivated pastures. In order to implement these measures, the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Pastures", adopted on May 21, 2019, the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated April 23, 2018 Resolution No. 299 "On measures for further improvement", Resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated November 7, 2018 No 914 "On the procedure for maintaining the state accounting of objects of flora and fauna, the volume of their use and the state cadastre" and the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated August 19, 2019 on the procedure for establishing norms of use, ensuring and maintaining the exchange of pastures "and other normative legal acts related to this activity.

Most of the location of the Republic of Karakalpakstan is in the desert region. The area of pastures and hayfields of the Republic of Karakalpakstan is 5.2 million hectares, which is 25% of the pastures of the Republic.

Despite the fact that many low-water-intensive crops and livestock are among the most important sectors of agriculture in Uzbekistan, they lag far behind other sectors of agriculture. The main reasons for this were the increased focus on cotton monoculture, the lack of irrigation water, and the secondary nature of animal husbandry..

Therefore, in order to increase the area and productivity of pastures, including cultural pastures, and to enrich pastures with water-resistant crops, to determine the productivity of pastures in Karakalpakstan, including cultural pastures, to determine the location of existing cultural pastures and it is an important task to determine the types of fertile crops to be included in pastures as a result of research.

As a result of the research, it was found that the first attempts to develop cultural pastures in the Republic of Karakalpakstan in Chimbay, Kegeyli,

Konlikul, Shumanay, Nukus districts, Amudarya and Takhiatash districts are planted on small areas.

The flora of the Republic of Karakalpakstan is less than in other regions of Uzbekistan due to water shortages, climate change and salinization of soils. On the basis of special research, the basis of natural and cultural pastures are reeds, licorice, wild alfalfa, wild clover, oats, apricots, cherkez, kandym, keurek, juusan and other plants. However, in the conditions of severe climate, saline soil and water scarcity of the Republic, the area of these plants is sharply reduced and very low yields are obtained. Therefore, new, promising, perennial and high-yielding varieties of corn "Azamat" in the direction of forage, "Vakhsh 10" in the direction of grain and fodder and "Chimbayskaya-Yubileynaya" in the fodder base of high-yielding corn of the Republic in the conditions of water shortage. it is advisable to enter.

In the first year of sowing, a new, promising, perennial and high-yielding variety of corn "Azamat" provided 3 harvests and yielded 687 ts / ha in each harvest. In recent years, this variety has yielded 691 ts / ha with 4 harvests and once used as pasture.

In addition, 4 varieties of corn "Vakhsh 10" and water hyacinth "Chimbayskaya-Yubileynaya" with a yield of 467 ts / ha in each harvest were used as 4 mowers and once as a pasture.

Conclusions and suggestions.

1. It is expedient to increase the area under new, promising, perennial and high-yielding varieties of corn "Azamat" in the field of fodder. In the first year of sowing, this variety provided 3 harvests and yielded 687 ts / ha in each harvest. In recent years, this variety has yielded 691 ts / ha with 4 harvests and once used as pasture.
2. "Vakhsh 10" corn and "Chimbayskaya-Yubileynaya" varieties of sudangrass were used as 4 pastures and once as a pasture with a yield of 467 ts / ha in each harvest.
3. It is expedient to develop animal husbandry along with the establishment of flora (saxaul, selenium, chogon, turanga, juusan and others) in the dry sea.
4. For the active use of sea salt, it is possible to benefit in every way by processing the salts on the spot and setting up the production of fertilizers.
5. It is necessary to create a lot of underground springs around the South Aral Sea and to create cultural pastures, to keep the flora and fauna in the snow.

References:

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